

IMPACT OF MARITAL QUALITY ON JOB PERFORMANCE: A GENDERED ANALYSIS OF CHAKWAL, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

In marriage, marital quality is a key element that has become the aspiration of every couple. But nowadays because the modern job market puts too much pressure on family life, Marital quality remains challenging for many people. This study sought to evaluate the level of marital quality and to determine its impact on job performance by measuring (communication, emotional support, intimacy and affection, trust and respect, and overall satisfaction) in the marital relationship between married employees of Chakwal district Punjab, Pakistan. The sample for this study includes 221 respondents (147 males and 76 females) selected through the random sampling technique. A self-administered questionnaire was designed for data collection which is divided into different parts. The data is analyzed through the SPSS and STATA. In this study estimation techniques like descriptive statistics, and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to analyse the data. These results show that there is a significant impact of marital quality on job performance. The overall findings indicate that female respondents have higher marital quality due to which their job performance increases as compared to males but there is a slight difference between both gender's marital quality and job performance while the sample ratio of females is less than the ratio of males. The study recommends that organizations should implement policies that will help to promote the work-life balance such as flexible hours of work and also the facility to remote work which will enhance the work-life balance and help to enhance marital quality which positively impacts the job performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Marriage is considered an important aspect of life, holding immense value in personal and social frameworks. According to a study by Hawkins et al. (2012), marriage is the foundation for emotional support because it offers a secure and caring atmosphere where couples can rely on one another during hard times. In addition to

promoting a sense of security and companionship, this emotional relationship also improves mental and emotional health. This contract of marriage represents a promise made by partners to help one another meet the challenges of life and promote stability and cohesiveness in families and society at large (Cherlin, 2010).

Married couples navigate the challenges of life together by establishing a framework for each other's development and growth through similar values, objectives, and life experiences (Umberson et al., 2006). The economic and judicial advantages of marriage such as inheritance rights and tax breaks offer concrete benefits that enhance the general well-being of married couples and their families (Lichter & Qian, 2008). Along with it, the social support network that comes with marriage, which includes friends and extended family, is a priceless asset in difficult times (DePaulo & Morris, 2005).

Understanding marital quality and marital disappointment is critical because it impacts work performance. Individuals who are with satisfying marriages have greater job satisfaction, productivity, and engagement. On the other hand, marital difficulties can increase stress, distraction, and absenteeism at work, all of which have a detrimental impact on their work performance. Promoting healthy marital relationships is therefore not only beneficial to individuals and families but also has broader implications for workplace productivity and well-being (Karney et al., 2016).

On the other hand, individuals with higher marital quality may experience less conflict between work and family roles, potentially leading to better work performance. It can be measured with the help of multiple dimensions like communication, emotional support, intimacy, affection, trust and respect, and overall marital satisfaction. These dimensions include both intrapersonal aspects, such as satisfaction and happiness, and interpersonal aspects, such as intimacy, and agreement. Some factors that influence marital quality range from personal characteristics such as personality and religiosity to interpersonal dynamics such as communication and economic status (Nurhayati et al., 2019).

However, countless internal (inside the family) and external pressures (outside the family) influence the quality of marriage and may ruin couples' lives and limit their capacity to perform effectively in the family, society, and at work. For instance, work-family conflicts affect their job

performance. Marital quality, including marital satisfaction and stability, can be negatively affected by divorce. For individuals who are struggling in their marriage, divorce may be the solution, which can impact their overall happiness and potentially lead to changes in career performance. The stress and confusion of divorce can harm work performance, especially if individuals struggle to cope with the emotional and practical challenges of marriage dissolution. Conversely, for some individuals, divorce may reduce marital tensions and improve work performance by reducing the distractions and stressors associated with an unhappy marriage (Univer, 2000). When individuals experience high levels of conflict between work and family roles, stress may increase and work performance may decline.

The impact of marital quality on job performance indicates a practical application and it is a real-life factor. Which explores how being married or single can affect an individual's productivity, motivation, job satisfaction, and overall performance at work. Married individuals may take on more responsibilities at their home that could potentially impact their work performance, while single individuals may have more flexibility and freedom to focus on their careers. There is also the possibility that married people may have better emotional support and stability, which can have a positive impact on work performance. On the other hand, single individuals may be more productive because they have more time and energy to devote to their work. One common belief is that a person's marital quality is important in influencing job performance (Sun et al., 2022).

Conflicting results from previous studies highlight the need for further investigation of the link between marital status and labor work performance to develop workforce diversity and equality policies. The complex relationship between marital quality and job performance is evident in the context of work-family boundaries. Marital satisfaction significantly impacts an individual's well-being and stress levels, and conflict surrounding work-family balance potentially affects both marital harmony and

career focus. A spouse's support and understanding of these challenges can positively impact job performance, while marital dissatisfaction can lead to decreased motivation and engagement at work (Frone et al., 2000).

To explore the impact of marital quality on the job performance of employees working in different places in Chakwal, the main objectives are stated below following objectives: Assess the level of marital quality among married workers. Determine the level of job performance of married workers. Explore the impact of marital quality and various dimensions on the job performance of employees working in different places in Chakwal. Conduct the gendered analysis to determine whether marital quality similarly or differently effecting job performance of male and female.

To check the impact of marital quality on the job performance of the respondent following hypotheses have been constructed.

HA1: There is a significant impact of various dimensions of marital quality on job performance of employees working in different places in Chakwal.

HA2: There is a significant difference between male and female work performance with different marital qualities.

It focuses on two issues such as work-family conflict and role conflict. Today, family and work are undoubtedly the two most essential responsibilities of every employee. Therefore, the question of how to balance the relationship between the two is becoming a hot topic for research. An employee's marital status is central to family relationships as satisfaction is a subjective or objective measure of an individual's life pattern. It affects not only individual and family well-being, but also performance in other areas, such as workplace behavior and job performance. In terms of work-family enrichment, close family relationships can contribute to work and the contribution of one role to another enriches the work-family relationship. It not only improves emotional support but also reduces stress and anxiety. It is a type of psychological resource that helps employees to maintain a good

state of mind. It motivates members' desire for self-growth and self-development through positive self-evaluation. Therefore, improving work-family work enriching it develops better work performance along with business performance (Atif, 2018).

2. Literature Review Theoretical Literature Review

The study uses relevant theories such as social exchange theory and work-conflict theory.

2.1. Social Exchange Theory

The social exchange theory is a social psychological theory that explains social relationships and interactions as a series of transactions where individuals seek to maximize rewards and minimize costs. According to the theory, individuals engage in relationships based on the principle of mutuality, where they expect that their actions will be similarly joined by others. The theory emphasizes the importance of trust, fairness, and mutual benefit in interpersonal relationships. It suggests that individuals are motivated to maintain relationships that offer positive outcomes. The theory also acknowledges the existence of power dynamics in social exchanges, where one party may have more resources or influence than the other, leading to irregular relationships. The theory has been applied in various fields, including organizational behaviours, economics, and sociology, to understand how individuals make decisions and interact with others in social contexts (Blanchard et al., 1997).

Through the perspective of social exchange theory, it can be implied that marital quality affects people's lives. This idea emphasizes the benefits of companionship, emotional support, and shared responsibilities for married people at the expense of the compromises and conflicts that come with keeping a marriage together. It also highlights the importance of a supportive marriage for general happiness and enjoyment which improves their work performance (Blanchard et al., 1997).

2.2. **Work-family Conflict Theory**

Work-family conflict was first studied in the late 19th century. During this period, work and income flowed from the family (farming) to outside the family (manufacturing). Industrialization complicated the relationship between work and family. Mostly, work-family conflict occurs when a person experiences a conflict between work and family responsibilities, making it difficult to balance both roles. This uncertainty can lead to conflicts at the work-life interface. In some cases, work-family conflict is associated with increased burnout, job stress, poor health, and problems with organizational commitment and performance (Colombo & Ghislieri, 2008).

Figure 2.1 shows that marital quality has a

significant relationship with job performance so when there is a negative marital relationship it will influence the job performance negatively. Figure 1 shows that when a negative relationship increases the work-family conflict it causes low marital satisfaction. When individuals experience poor marital quality they face high emotional strain and conflict at home which can spill over their work life. The emotional distress leads to decreased focus and motivation for work which results in lower job performance. Distraction and stress cause absenteeism and disengagement at work which cause poor job performance. Marital dissatisfaction supports work-family conflict and negatively impacts both personal and professional life.

Figure2.1: Work-Family Conflict Theory

Source: Compiles from different studies.

Empirical Literature Review

This comprehensive literature review examines numerous studies that investigated the impact of marital quality on job performance, shedding light specifically examined how marital quality affects job performance. There are millions of couples who are committed to relationships around the world. The longevity of marriage largely depends on marital quality, so here examine these studies to check the level of marital quality between married employees.

This study by Greenstein, (2016) inspects the relationship between gender, marital status, and life satisfaction. The study used data from the World Values Survey and the European values across 2006 -2014 with a sample of 103,217 respondents across 81 nations. The findings of this study suggest that women and men display similar levels of life satisfaction. Overall gender moderates the impact of various socio-demographic factors. The findings of this study suggest that women and men display equal levels of life e satisfaction. The gender moderates the effect of various socio-demographic factors but the main focus is on the significant gender differences which detected the impact of marital status on life satisfaction. The large-scale survey method is adapted by using econometric techniques such as regression analysis to explore this relationship.

This study by Barrett, (2016) examined the impact of marital status on mental health, focusing on marital trajectory, including past marital loss, number and type, and duration of current marital status. This study utilizes data from the National Institute's Piedmont Health Survey, a large health survey conducted in 1982-83 among 2,158 people. The study found that the loss of a previous marriage affected current marital status and mental health. Multiple losses have negative effects on mental health, depending on marital status. For analysis, this study used an econometric technique, and regression analysis to evaluate this relationship while controlling for demographic variables.

Ashwini (2018) examines work-life balance, marital satisfaction, and spousal attachment of

407 employed people in Tamil Nadu, India. The study used a convenience sampling technique and the survey was conducted on participants aged 25 to 45, married for more than three years, and currently employed. The study employed the SPSS analysis showing the detrimental effects of unbalanced work-life dynamics. Results of the research showed a significant negative correlation between work-life balance and marital satisfaction. This study also highlighted spousal attachment as an intermediary in the relationship between marital satisfaction and trait mindfulness and the complex interplay of individual traits, relationship dynamics, and external stressors on marital well-being in Tamil Nadu.

Wang et al. (2018) examine the principal's job satisfaction with the magnification of the work. Frederick Herz Berg's two-factor theory was used to shed light on the factors that play a role in motivating and maintaining a principal's job satisfaction. Logistic multiple regressions were used for the analysis of the survey. The data was collected from the 2,701 respondents who belong to the elementary and secondary school principals' council in Ontario Canada. From all of the samples, approximately 1,423 valid cases were used for the data analysis. The finding of the study shows that as the work intensity increases, motivating factors such as workplace difficulties, and recognition from employers, and work demands and maintenance while external factors such as external policy influence, organizational support, and the principal's relationships with teachers, and labor unions have a significant impact on principal job satisfaction. These factors influence student achievement and the extent to which they can effectively contribute to improving school performance.

Hafeez et al. (2020) examined the relationship between marital status and job performance among academic faculty in universities in the district of Shaheed Benazir Abad, with gender as a moderating variable. Data collection involved a sample of two hundred respondents from three universities, analyzed using SPSS software. The study found a positive and significant association between marital status and job performance,

indicating that being married may positively impact employee performance. The research used the method of the “Mann-Whitney” test for predictor and outcome variables and regression analysis for the moderating variable. These statistical techniques allowed for a detailed examination of the link between marital status and job performance in the academic sector, providing valuable insights into employee dynamics in this context.

Tumsarp et al., (2020) consider the impact of marital status on female labor force participation in developing countries, with a particular focus on Thailand. The study found that married women in Thailand participate more in the labor market and work longer hours compared to single women. This is especially true among younger, less educated, non-household heads and women with fewer family responsibilities. There is no specific technique mentioned for sampling, and this study used an instrumental variable technique with six ratios at the local serving as instrumental variables to address concerns about marital status and labor market participation. This method allows us to estimate causal effects.

Hussain and Ahmad, (2021) examine the relationship between mindfulness, procrastination, and work performance among employees in an organizational setting, by focusing on the controlling role of marital status. This study utilized a sampling of 400 employees of a telecommunications company. This study conducted correlation and mediation analyses to examine the relationships between these variables. Results show a significant relationship between these variables, with marital status acting as a moderating factor.

Gattig et al., (2021) address the relationship between marriage and life satisfaction by using panel data from the (pairfam), a German Family Panel. By adding all the trajectories into fixed effect regression. This study found that whether marriage itself influences life satisfaction or individual baseline satisfaction is more likely to be married. The analysis of this study reveals that ordinary least square regression over-emphasizes the impact of marriage on life satisfaction. While

on the other hand fixed effect estimation suggests a lower impact on marriage and implies a more understanding of this relationship.

Nagargoje et al. (2022) study explored how marital status and lifestyle moderate the relationship between social participation and life satisfaction. This study is conducted on 31,464 Indian older adults from the Longitudinal Aging Study in India. This study used descriptive statistics, bivariate analysis, and multivariate linear regression to highlight the importance of social policies to increase life satisfaction among older adults in India. Results of this study indicate that older men had higher life satisfaction, and social participation, marital union, and co-residence had a positive effect on life satisfaction. Social participation was especially helpful for married individuals and those living with their families.

This study investigates that there is the negative impact of work-family conflict on work performance, by focusing on emotional intelligence Bhatti and Batool (2024). For this study data from 250 banking sector employees in Beijing were analyzed by using multiple regression analysis, SPSS, and AMOS. The findings of this research show that there is a significant negative relationship between family-work conflict, and work performance, The Practical implications of this work suggest the value of emotional intelligence training is essential for resolving work-family conflict and improving work performance in the Chinese banking sector.

In a nutshell, the literature shows that marriage quality is connected to several facets of personal life. It has the potential to alter a person's life, social relationships, motivation, courage, and, ultimately, work performance. Further, through affecting life satisfaction, well-being, and participation in the market it affects job performance. This study contributes to the literature in multiple ways. First, the study offers evidence-based insights regarding marital quality and job performance by taking the multiple dimensions of marital quality. Second, the study considers the difference based on gender and how male and females with different marital

qualities perform their jobs.

3. Methodology

The study presents a theoretical framework and the estimation techniques used for the study are descriptive statistics and the non-parametric test (Wilcoxon signed rank test).

Theoretical Framework

In this section, we examined the impact of marital status on labor work performance and for that, a theoretical framework based on literature has been established. Figure 3.1 represents the impact of marital quality on job performance which shows that marital quality increases emotional well-being which will help to reduce stress and lead to a better spousal relationship and makes a positive impact on health.

Figure 3.1: Theoretical Framework

When there is an increase in emotional well-being then there is a satisfying marriage which leads to (emotional stability and happiness), stress management maintains a healthy relationship, and a better spousal relationship leads to a supportive relationship that offers encouragement understanding, and advice while the health has a positive impact on physical outcomes. A satisfying marriage will help to handle workplace stress and challenges. Maintaining a healthy relationship will help to do clear thinking, motivate for work, and also

increase productivity at work. A supportive spousal relationship also offers encouragement understanding, and advice that will help to enhance confidence, motivation, and resilience to work. Similarly, better physical health has positive outcomes that will help to reduce absenteeism and enhance energy levels which lead to better job performance.

4. Data

The data has been collected through a questionnaire which is subdivided into 4

sections. A questionnaire was developed to obtain survey data. Keeping the central objective of the study in mind, the study adopted close-ended and open-ended questions to obtain sufficient relevant information.

Section A is about personal information which contains information related to the respondent's age, marital status, gender, economic status, household head, number of years of working, family type, and location of residence, etc. Section B contains information regarding marriage and household relationships i.e., how long have the respondent married, the age at the time of marriage, whether having children or not or wants to plan children in the future, living with the spouse and spouse's family and relationship with the parents of the spouse. Section C explores marital quality and contains information regarding communication, emotional support, intimacy and affection, trust and respect, and overall satisfaction of married

couples. Section D encloses the information related to the job performance of the respondents.

Survey Description and Sample Criterion

To understand and check the reliability of the questionnaire instruments by the participants, the questionnaire was distributed among friends and teachers before conducting the final survey. After making the required changes, the primary data is collected through survey-based interviews. For analysis, the primary data of 221 respondents was collected from the city of Chakwal. The population of the study consists of married employees who belong to the city Chakwal and work with different sectors like schools, colleges, banks, NGEOS, and different Pakistan forces like the Army, Air Force Atomic, and Police. In 2024, data was collected randomly using a simple random sampling technique.

Table 4.1: Description of Variables

Variables	Definition
JP	= job performance
MQ	= Marital Quality

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results Based on Descriptive Analysis

In descriptive statistics, data is analyzed by using the frequency distribution of respondents

regarding the demographic characteristics, which include gender, age, employment status, family type, and economic or financial situation.

Figure 5.1: Distribution of the Respondents Regarding Gender

Source: Authors Estimations.

Figure 5.1 indicates the results of the gender distribution of males and females which shows that there are 65.6% male and 34.4% female in

the data set indicating that females are less than males and males are the predominant gender in the data set.

Fig 5.2: Distribution of the Respondents Regarding Employment

Source: Author's calculation.

Fig 5.2 illustrates the employment status of respondents indicating that the majority of individuals in the dataset are working full-time. The statistics indicate that 81% of respondents were employed full-time, 10% were employed part-time and the remaining 9% were self-employed. The overall results show that a small

portion of the population is engaged in part-time and self-employment compared to full-time work. Table 5.1 indicates that the minimum age of the respondents was 21 years and the maximum age of the respondent was greater than 60 years. The statistics show that 29.9 % of the respondents belonged to the 21-30 age group, 34.4% belonged

to the age of 31-40 years, 19.9% belonged to the age group of 41-50, 7.7% people belonged to the age interval of 51-60 and the remaining 5% were above 60 years. The statistics indicate that 65.2% of respondents were from joint families that adhered to Pakistan’s deeply rooted culture. Out

of 221 respondents, 33.9% of respondents were from nuclear families, and 9% of respondents belonged to the extended family highlighting a portion of families include additional relatives in a household.

Table 5.1: The Demographic Characteristics of the Respondent

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
21-30	66	29.9
31-40	76	34.4
41-50	44	19.9
51-60	17	7.7
> 60	1	.5
Family Type		
Nuclear	75	33.9
Joint	144	65.2
Extended	2	9
Economic Status		
Upper Class	14	6.3
Middle Class	186	84.2
Lower Class	21	9.5
Area		
Rural	147	66.5
Urban	74	33.5
Household Head		
Self	107	48.4
Father	50	22.6
Mother	5	2.3
Husband	59	26.7
Financial Situation		
Excellent	12	5.4
Good	109	49.3
Fair	89	40.3
Poor	10	4.5
Very Poor	1	10.5
Total	221	100

Source: Authors’ Calculation.

Moreover, Table 5.1 also postulates the economic status of the respondents. 6.3% of respondents in a sample belong to the upper class, 84.2% belong to the middle class and 9.5% people belong to the lower class. The statistics indicate that the majority of the respondents belong to the middle class. Further results show that 66.5% of

respondents live in rural areas and 33.5% live in urban areas. The table also indicates that 48.4% of respondents are the head of the family, 22.6% of respondents are headed by their father, 2.3% of respondents’ household head is their mother and the remaining 26.7% of the respondent’s head of household is their husband.

Statistics also show the financial situation of the respondents. Results show that only 5.4% of the respondents have an excellent financial situation, 49.3 % have a good financial situation, 40.3% have a fair financial situation, 4.5% have a poor financial situation and the remaining 10.5% have an impoverished financial situation. The statistics reveal that most households have either a good or fair financial situation. A small fraction of households has excellent, poor, and very poor financial conditions.

Results Based on Non-Parametric Test

There are two non-parametric techniques are applied namely the Wilcoxon Rank Sum (WRS) test and the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Sum (WSRS) test. To make comparisons for two unrelated samples Wilcoxon rank sum test is used. For two related samples, while Wilcoxon signed test is

used. Here we apply only the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Sum (WSRS) test.

Wilcoxon Signed Rank Sum Test

In the present section, we will discuss the results based on the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Sum test in detail across gender, area, age, job type, economic status, family type, organization of work, and household size.

Table 5.2 shows the Wilcoxon Test results, which compares job performance across the different demographic variables. So according to the results of this table, we will reject the null hypothesis which indicates that there is a change in job performance across age, gender, area, job type, economic status, family type organization of work, and household size and these all results are significant at 1% (Kalia, & Bhardwaj, 2019).

Table 5.2: Comparison of job Performance across Demographic Variables

Hypothesis	Results
	Job Performance
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on respondent age.	12.387*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance of respondents based on their genders.	13.148*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance of the respondents based on the area in which they live.	13.063*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on job types.	13.040*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on economic status of respondent.	13.002*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on family types.	13.054*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on the organization in which respondent is working.	12.873*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on household size.	9.395*** (0.00)

Source: Authors own estimation: The significance level of the estimate is: ***, **, and * represent 1, 5, and 10 percent significant levels, respectively.

Table 5.3 compares the change in job performance across marriage and household relationships of the respondents. The results indicated we would reject the null hypothesis because there is a change in job performance

across years of marriage, age at the time of marriage, having children, living in the same household or not, the factors that influence the decision of marriage and to managing conflict with spouse family. These all factors contribute to

the change in the job performance of the respondent and the results are significant at 1%. Working women’s job performance and

efficiency will slow down with the birth of a child while this is not the same for men (Healy & Rossin, 2021).

Table 5.3: Comparison of job Performance across Marriage and Household Relationship

Hypothesis	Results
	Job Performance
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on the duration of marriage.	-12.574*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on the age at the time of marriage.	-11.201*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on the factors that influencing the marriage decision.	-8.970*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on couple’s number of children.	-13.065*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based couple’s living status in the same house.	-12.953*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on the reasons due to which couple not living in the same house.	-6.526*** (0.00)
H0: There is no variation in job performance based on managing conflict with the spouse’s family.	-12.318*** (0.00)

Source: Authors own estimation: The significance level of the estimate is: ***, **, and * represent 1, 5, and 10 percent significant levels, respectively.

Table 5.4 compares the change in the job performance of female and male respondents. This table uses the different dimensions of marital quality in which COM is communication, ES is emotional support, INT &

AFF is intimacy and Affection, TR & RES is trust and respect, OVS is overall satisfaction and OVR MQ & JP is the overall marital quality and job performance.

Table 5.4: Comparison of Marital Quality across Female Gender

Hypothesis	Results					
	COM	ES	INT & AFF	TR& RES	OVS	OVR MQ & Gender
H0: There is no change in the marital quality across the female gender.	-7.509*** (0.000)	-7.490*** (0.000)	-7.549*** (0.000)	-7.509*** (0.000)	-7.651*** (0.000)	-7.534*** (0.000)

Comparison of Marital Quality across Male Gender

Hypothesis	Results					
	COM	ES	INT & AFF	TR& RES	OVS	OVR MQ & JP
H0: There is no change in the marital quality across the male gender.	-10.741 ^{***} (0.000)	-10.627 ^{***} (0.000)	-10.617 ^{***} (0.000)	-10.698 ^{***} (0.000)	-10.705 ^{***} (0.000)	-10.475 ^{***} (0.000)

Source: Authors own estimation: The significance level of the estimate is: ^{***}, ^{**}, and ^{*} represent 1, 5, and 10 percent significant levels, respectively.

The results of the table indicate that we will reject the null hypothesis because there is a change in the job performance across the marital quality of male and female respondents and the results are

significant at 1%. The results postulate that there is a significant impact of marital quality on job performance for both females and males (Rogers & May, 2003).

Table 5.5: Comparison of Job Performance and Marital Quality

Hypothesis	Results			
	Communicat	Trust respect	Overall satisfacti	MQ and JP
There is no change in e job performance ross marital quality.	-2.621 ^{***} (0.009)	4.530 ^{***} (0.000)	-4.108 ^{***} (0.000)	-2.466 ^{***} (0.014)

Source: Authors own estimation: The significance level of the estimate is: ^{***}, represents 1 percent significant levels.

Table 5.5 shows the results of job performance across the marital quality. Here we reject the null hypothesis because there is a change in job performance across marital quality at the 1% significant level. Marital quality plays a major role in employees' job performance because work-

family priorities conflict affects the performance of employees. When there is a supportive marital relationship employee job performance increases with this work-life balance is also a necessary component for better and more efficient job performance (Mwangi et al., 2016).

Table 5.6: Comparison of Job Performance of Male and Female Respondents

Hypothesis		
Job Performance of Male	H0: There is no change in job performance across the male gender.	-10.795 ^{***} (0.000)
Job Performance of Female	H0: There is no change in job performance across the female gender.	-7.696 ^{***} (0.000)

Source: Authors own estimation: The significance level of the estimate is: ^{***}, ^{**}, and ^{*} represent 1, 5, and 10 percent significant levels, respectively.

Table 5.6 shows the comparison of the job performance of male and female employees working with the different sectors (public, private, NGOS). The results of this table provide an indication of rejecting the null hypothesis because there is a change in the job performance of both genders and the results are significant at 1 %. Job performance is changed due to organizational support, organizational commitment, and less turnover intentions from the job leads to better job performance (Rutherford et al., 2012).

Conclusion

The study uses primary data by using a sample random technique. The analysis has been carried out by taking data from 221 married employees from the city of Chakwal. The analysis has been performed by using descriptive statistics, and non-parametric tests. The study findings reveal that the majority of respondents were male the ratio of males is 65.6% while the ratio of females is 34.4%. The majority of the respondents lived in rural areas of the city of Chakwal. The study concluded that marital quality has a positive impact on the job performance of the respondents. The results of this study also indicate that women have a greater marital quality due to which their job performance also increases as compared to males.

The results also indicate that demographic characteristics have a significant relation with job performance. The majority of the female respondents were satisfied with their marital quality, 73 females out of total 76 are satisfied with their marital quality due to which their job performance increased and only 3 females' marital quality did not increase. While 139 males among 145 have an increase in marital quality due to this their job performance increased and only 6 males' marital quality did not increase due to which their job performance also did not increase. The results of this study show that there is a slight difference between the marital quality and job performance of males and females.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following are some recommendations.

- The organization should implement policies that will help to promote the work-life balance such as flexible hours of work, options for telecommuting, and family-focused leave policies in any certain situation. This will enhance the work-life balance which will help to enhance the marital quality which positively impacts the job performance.
- The organizations introduce employee assistance programs (EAPs) which provide counselling services to the employees for relationship management and family issues which help the employees to manage marital relationship challenges which leads to better and more effective job performance.

Limitations

This study was limited in the Chakwal due to time and cost constraints. With this, the finding is also limited by the sample population. For instance, geographical, socioeconomic, and cultural differences may affect the dynamics of relationships and also their impact on job performance. While marital quality is a significant factor other variables such as job satisfaction, and emotional well-being can also play a major role in determining job performance. So, the study can overlook these intersections in the future.

REFERENCES

- Atif, T., & Zubairi, S. A. (2018). Impact of marital status on job satisfaction, organizational commitment and work life balance: A study on employees working in banking sector of Pakistan. *The Islamic Culture " As-Saqafat-ul Islamia" Research Journal-Sheikh Zayed Islamic Centre, University of Karachi*, (40).
- Ashwini, U. R. (2018). Work-life balance and marital satisfaction among working men and women. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 5(4), 988-992.

- Bhatti, A. H., & Batool, T. (2024). Impact of Work-Family conflict, Family to Work conflict on job performance: Moderating role of emotional intelligence. *Curr Trends Business Mgmt*, 2(1), 01-09.
- Barrett, A. E. (2000). Marital trajectories and mental health. *Journal of health and social behavior*, 451-464.
- Blanchard, F.A., & Bartusch, D.J. (1997). The relationship between marital quality and job satisfaction: A review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 59(3), 574-593.
- Colombo, L., & Ghislieri, C. (2008). The work-to-family conflict: Theories and measures. *work*, 15(1), 35-55.
- Cherlin, A. J. (2010). Demographic trends in the United States: A review of research in the 2000s. *Journal of marriage and family*, 72(3), 403-419.
- DePaulo, B. M., & Morris, W. L. (2005). AUTHORS' RESPONSE: Should Singles and the Scholars Who Study Them Make Their Mark or Stay in Their Place?. *Psychological Inquiry*, 16(2-3), 142-149.
- Frone, M. R., Russell, M., & Cooper, M. L. (2000). Prevalence of work-family conflict: Are work and family boundaries asymmetrically permeable. *Women Employees and Human Resource Management*, 723, 172.
- Gattig, A., & Minkus, L. (2021). Does Marriage Increase Couples' Life Satisfaction? Evidence Using Panel Data and Fixed-effects Individual Slopes. *Comparative Population Studies- Zeitschrift für Bevölkerungswissenschaft*, 46, 123-148.
- Greenstein, Theodore N. 2016. "Gender, Marital Status, and Life Satisfaction: A Cross-National Study." *North Carolina State University*.
- Hawkins, A. J., Stanley, S. M., Blanchard, V. L., & Albright, M. (2012). Exploring programmatic moderators of the effectiveness of marriage and relationship education programs: A meta-analytic study. *Behavior therapy*, 43(1), 77-87.
- Hafeez, M., Ahamd Khawar Shahzad, A., Din, M. U., Aslam, W., & Khan, M. (2020). Evaluating the Impact of Marital Status on Employees' Job Performance: Moderating Role of Hired Hand's Gender. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(11), 1699-1706.
- Hussain, M. M., & Ahmad, Z. (2021). Moderating Effect of Marital Status among Mindfulness, Procrastination and Job Performance of Employees. *Review of Education, Administration & Law*, 4(1), 133-143.
- Healy, O., Heissel, J., & Rossin-Slater, M. (2021, June). Baby bumps in the road: The impact of parenthood on job performance and career advancement. In *10th Annual Conference of the American Society of Health Economists*. ASHECON.
- Kalia, N., & Bhardwaj, B. (2019). Contextual and task performance: do demographic and organizational variables matter?. *Rajagiri Management Journal*, 13(2), 30-42.
- Karney, B. R., & Bradbury, T. N. (1995). The longitudinal course of marital quality and stability: A review of theory, methods, and research. *Psychological bulletin*, 118(1), 3.
- Lichter, D. T., & Qian, Z. (2008). Serial cohabitation and the marital life course. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 70(4), 861-878.
- Mwangi, L., Boinett, C. C., Tumwet, E., & Bowen, D. (2016). Effects of Work life Balance on Employees Performance in Institutions of Higher Learning: A Case Study of Kabarak University. *Kabarak Journal of Research & Innovation*, 4(2), 60-69.
- Ndayambaje, E., Pierewan, A. C., Nizeyumukiza, E., Nkundimana, B., & Ayriza, Y. (2020). Marital status and subjective well-being: Does education level take into account. *Cakrawala Pendidikan*, 39(1), 120-132.
- Nurhayati, S. R., Faturachman, F., & Helmi, A. F. (2019). Marital quality: A conceptual review. *Buletin Psikologi*, 27(2), 109-124.

- Rutherford, B. N., Wei, Y., Park, J., & Hur, W. M. (2012). Increasing job performance and reducing turnover: An examination of female Chinese salespeople. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 20(4), 423-436.
- Rogers, S. J., & May, D. C. (2003). Spillover between marital quality and job satisfaction: Long-term patterns and gender differences. *Journal of Marriage and family*, 65(2), 482-495.
- Sun, L., Mao, Z., & Zhou, J. (2022). The Effect of Employees' Marital Satisfaction on Job Performance: Based on the Perspective of Conservation of Resource Theory. *Computer Science & Technology Trends*, 23-34.
- Tumsarp, P., & Pholphirul, P. (2020). Does marriage discourage female labor force participation? Empirical evidence from Thailand. *Marriage & Family Review*, 56(7), 677-688.
- Wang, F., Pollock, K. E., & Hauseman, C. (2018). School principals' job satisfaction: The effects of work intensification. *Canadian Journal of Educational Administration and Policy*, 185, 73.
- Univor, A. E. (2000). Marital trajectories and mental health. *Journal of health and social behavior*, 451-464.
- Umberson, D., Williams, K., Powers, D. A., Liu, H., & Needham, B. (2006). You make me sick: Marital quality and health over the life course. *Journal of health and social behavior*, 47(1), 1-16.

